

Supplemental table 1. RT-PCR mouse primers of genes.

Fibronectin Forward	AATGGTGCCTTGTGCCACTTCC
Fibronectin Reverse	ATGTTGTCCCGCCTACCCTCA
Collagen I Forward	GCTCAGAGGCGAAGGCAACAG
Collagen I Reverse	GATGGGCAG GCGGGAGGTC
Tgfb1 Forward	CTCCCGTGGCTTCTAGTGC
Tgfb1 Reverse	GCCTTAGTTTGGACAGGATCTG
β -Actin Forward	GGCTGTATTCCCCTCCATCG
β -Actin Reverse	CCAGTTGGTAACAATGCCATG T
Fcnb Forward	CCCGAATTCCCAGCCATGGCCCTGGGATCT
Fcnb Reverse	CCCCTCGAGCTAGATGAGCCGCACCTTCAT

Supplemental table 2. Mouse primers of targeted knock-out genes.

KO Forward	CTACTTTGTGGCTGCCACATCC	391bp
KO Reverse	TCGACAGGGTTTCTCTGAATAGCC	
WT Forward	TCATTCCCAAGCAGTCCCCTC	455bp
WT Reverse	GTCAAGGCATCTGGTGTACACGG	

Supplemental figure legends

Supplemental figure 1. Expression of Fcnb in pulmonary fibrosis mice with bleomycin (BLM) induction. (A) Representative results for co-immunostaining of Fcnb and Fsp1 (myofibroblast marker) in lung sections from BLM-induction mice. The nuclei were stained blue using 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI), and the images were taken under original magnification $\times 400$.

Supplemental figure 2. Validation of knock-out Fcnb in mice. (A) PCR analysis of tail DNA to determine the presence of the knock-out allele. (B) Representative results for co-immunostaining of Fcnb and Epcam in lung sections derived from wild type (WT) and Fcnb knock-out (*Fcnb*^{-/-}) mice. The nuclei were stained DAPI, and the images were taken under original magnification $\times 400$. (C) RT-PCR analysis of Fcnb in the lungs of WT and *Fcnb*^{-/-} mice ($n=6-10$ per group). Data are presented as mean \pm SEM. * $p<0.05$, ** $p<0.01$, *** $p<0.001$ by one-way ANOVA (C).

Supplemental figure 3. Differently expressed genes between WT and Fcnb knock-out (*Fcnb*^{-/-}) mice with BLM induction. (A) Hierarchical clustering of samples in *Fcnb*^{-/-} vs. WT groups with the significantly differently expressed genes. (B) The volcano plot showed the distribution of differently expressed genes.

Supplemental figure 4. Validation of overexpression Fcnb in mice. (A) The timeline of the experiment. (B) Western blot analysis of Fcnb in lung tissue lysates derived from wild type (WT) and Fcnb over-expressed (OE-*Fcnb*) mice ($n=3-6$ per group). (C) RT-PCR analysis of Fcnb in the lungs of WT and OE-*Fcnb* mice ($n=6-15$ per group). Data are presented as mean \pm SEM. * $p<0.05$, ** $p<0.01$, *** $p<0.001$ by one-way ANOVA (C).

Supplemental figure 1

Supplemental figure 2

Supplemental figure 3

Supplemental figure 4

